

Digital solutions in modern power substations

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Abstract— The increased share of distributed RES energy sources forces significant changes in the operation of power grids in order to ensure the stability of the entire energy system. This requires the development of new measurement, control and monitoring systems operating in real time to ensure network protection. The increased share of prosumers also requires fair settlement for the supplied and used electricity.

Keywords— IEC 61850, digitalization of power substations, digital instrument transformers, SAMU, sampled values SV

I. INTRODUCTION

The stability of the power system has so far been based on basic generating units, which stabilize the network frequency in a closely coordinated manner. Large synchronous generators, which are rotating machines with high inertia, enable stabilization of the voltage and frequency of the network. In the event of a frequency disturbance, they can actively correct it by releasing their kinetic energy of rotation in accordance with the needs of the electrical grid. Moving away from fossil fuels in the production of electricity and reducing energy from conventional coal-fired power plants is of particular importance for the energy system, due to the reduction of the inertia of the electrical grid. This balance can be achieved by using distributed, fast-access energy storage. Change of electricity production profile to RES (Renewable Energy Sources) requires the introduction of new technical solutions and verification of those used so far. With the development of Ethernet networks and their effective protection against cyberattacks, digital measuring equipment is increasingly replacing analog equipment in power stations. Digital measurement equipment requires the development of a new metrological infrastructure for monitoring measurements and standardizing digital substation equipment such as transformers with digital output and SAMU (Stand Alone Merging Unit), a device that combines electrical information from instrument transformers and then makes it available in the form of a digital data stream SV (Sampled

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Values). Digitalization of measurement signals allows for cost reduction of wiring, which in analogue substations was the basis for the operation of protection and control devices. In digital substations, data is transmitted via an Ethernet link, creating a so-called process bus, and delivered to the target device via a system of network switches.

II. ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT OF OF TRADITIONAL MV POWER SUBSTATIONS

Power substations are the basic elements of every system supplying electricity. Correct selection of distribution fields and control and measurement equipment ensures safe operation of the entire power station and continuity of supply, while maintaining basic parameters of electrical energy quality. Switchboards, e.g. MV, consist of a busbar system mounted on insulators. They are equipped with switchgear (CB's circuit breakers, DS's disconnectors, ES's earthing switches), measuring current instrument transformers CT's and voltage instrument transformers VT's and mechanical interlocking and protection systems. A typical view of a distribution field [1] is presented in a single-line diagram in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Single-line diagram of a feeder field

The switchboard is divided into sections called distribution fields. Due to the function and equipment they perform, we divide them into supply, coupling, measuring, and outgoing. For the needs of control, supervision, and protection, IED devices (Intelligent Electronic Device) are used. They monitor the operation of the distribution bay via secondary circuits. Information about currents and voltages is obtained from instrument transformers. Standardized current and voltage measuring transformers are commonly used to assess the parameters of the electricity network in power substations. Current instrument transformers CT's typically have analog output with a nominal current of 1 or 5 A [2]. Voltage instrument transformers VT's usually provide analog output with a nominal voltage on the secondary side of $100\text{ V}/\sqrt{3}$. There are also low-power current transformers LPCT and low-power voltage transformers LPVT compliant with IEC 61869-6 [12]. For example LPVT can have nominal secondary voltage $3,25\text{ V}/\sqrt{3}$.

III. DIGITAL MEASUREMENT INTERFACES IN MODERN POWER SUBSTATIONS

To standardize the transmission of data concerning analog signals in digital form, the IEC 61869 and IEC 61850 series of standards have been developed. Digital samples of analog signals, referred to as Sampled Values (SVs), are time with UTC time scale. For this reason, a time synchronization signal, e.g. in the form of a 1PPS pulse from a GPS receiver, must be provided to SAMU devices. Digital solutions for substation instrumentation ensure sampling of current and voltage values in accordance with the IEC 61869 standard and their transmission via an Ethernet or fiber optic link in accordance with the IEC 61850 standard [2]. The IEC 61869-9 [3] standard describes the requirements for the digital interface of measuring transformers, while the IEC 61869-13 [4] standard describes the requirements for the SAMU connecting unit, which performs the transmission of sampled SV signals in consecutive Ethernet frames. An example of how measurement results are presented within a single frame is shown in Table I.

TABLE I. THE METHOD OF PRESENTING MEASUREMENTS IN THE ETHERNET FRAME

Header	IEC61850 Sampled Values APPID: 0x4000 Length: 110 Reserved 1: 0x8000 (32768), Simulated Reserved 2: 0x0000 (0) savPdu noASDU: 1 seqASDU: 1 item
Application Service Data Unit	ASDU svID: SAMU01 smpCnt: 1706 confRev: 1 smpSynch: none (0) PhsMeas1
Sample I1 with flag	value: -20365 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample I2 with flag	value: -6127 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample I3 with flag	value: -4728 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process

Sample I0 with flag	value: -7 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample U1 with flag	value: -429565 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample U2 with flag	value: -11190 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample U3 with flag	value: 462506 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process
Sample U0 with flag	value: 7250 quality: 0x00000000, validity: good, source: process

The IEC 61869-9 [3] standard for measuring transformers also specifies the structure of SV streams sent to the process bus. However, the IEC 61850 [2] standards are too general, so the protection manufacturers have developed a guide to IEC 61850-9-2 [5] which is a recommendation for the method of presenting and transmitting sample streams. Two standards have been adopted: 80 samples per period for protection and 256 samples per period for measurement purposes. This guide precisely specifies the method of presenting data in Ethernet frames: 3 phase currents measurements and the I0 current and 3 phase voltages measurements and the U0 voltage. The guide also details parameters such as: stream name, data type, number of structures with samples (ASDU) in a single frame. This has significantly simplified the establishment of communication between devices from different manufacturers [6]. Devices distributing SV are identified in the network by their MAC number. Instrument transformers with a digital interface are increasingly being adopted in power substations. Analog measurement signals are sampled and sent in digital form in the SV format over the power substation Ethernet network. The IEC 61850-9-2 standard [6] describes how this data should be formatted in Ethernet frames. Each single sample value is recorded in a 32-bit register. The MSB bit indicates the polarity of the signal. Analog measurement values in the samples always refer to the primary side. The presentation of measurement data of voltage and current measurement signals, taking into account the measurement range and measurement error, in the sample register is shown in figures 2 and 3.

Fig. 2. Presentation of phase voltage measurement data in the sample register

Fig.3. Presentation of current measurement data in the sample register

According to the standard, the resolution for phase currents I_f and leakage currents to earth I_0 is 1 mA. The resolution for phase voltages U_f and Zero Sequence Voltage U_0 is 10 mV. This allows measurement with a wide dynamic range—up to 65 times I_n for currents and 2.5 times U_n for voltages. The number of unused lower bits depends on the accuracy class of the instrument transformer. The requirements presented in the IEC 61869-13 standard [4] describe the permissible amplitude and phase limit errors introduced by the SAMU device. The class of the device is determined within the measurement range, expressed as a percentage of the nominal value. For SAMU class 0.2, the permissible current ratio measurement error is $\pm 0.2\%$ and phase error ± 10 min within the (0.2% - 400%) range of the nominal current. Measurement signals from instrument transformers (current and voltage) are delivered to SAMU, which converts them into digital data in SV format and then sends them to the process bus according to the 61850-9-2 protocol [6], as shown in figure 4. To enable the correct time stamping of SV values, it is required to deliver a 1PPS signal related to the UTC time scale to the time synchronization input of SAMU devices. A device with an interface sending SV streams compliant with the IEC 61869-9 [3] standard must be able to configure data streams according to IEC 61850-9-2. The SAMU device can be configured to generate frames defined by various applicable standards and implementation guides for digital SV communication.

Fig. 4. Example of digital interface in power substations

The notation $FfSsIiUu$ is used to identify different frames, where:

f - sampling rate expressed in samples per second,

s - number of ASDUs (Application Service Data Units) in each frame,

i - number of current channels in each ASDU,

u - number of voltage channels in each ASDU.

The SV data stream frames have been defined and described in the IEC 61869-9 [3] standard, e.g.:

- F4000S1I4U4 for 50 Hz - 80 samples per period,
- F4800S1I4U4 for 60 Hz - 80 samples per period.
- F12800S8I4U4 for 50 Hz - 256 samples per period.
- F15360S8I4U4 for 60 Hz - 256 samples per period.

ASDU should be understood as an application service data unit, e.g. for transmitting information between IED devices and substation supervision devices.

IV. TESTING THE SAMU DEVICE AT THE TESTBED

A commercial class 0.2 SAMU device was tested. A measurement testbed was prepared to evaluate the voltage ratio error and phase displacement error of the device. The source of voltage and current signals was the CMC356 Omicron calibrator. It was selected due to the possibility of time synchronization using a PTP time server via a 10 MHz signal. Analog signals were fed to the measurement inputs of the calibrated SAMU device and the reference device. The digital signal from the calibrated SAMU was fed to the digital SV input of the reference device. The signal from the time server was distributed to all devices that needed it using PTP time converter type Omicron Ticro 100 which provided 1PPS and 10 MHz signals. The reference standard for the tested SAMU device was a WM3000U type measuring bridge [7]. It was used in both the voltage and current measurement setups due to the lack of a special setup for current measurement. In the current measurement setup, in order to obtain a voltage signal, which was necessary as a reference signal for the WM3000U bridge, precision measuring resistors type A40B Fluke [8] were used. Figure 5 shows a photograph of the testbed for the SAMU measurements.

Fig. 5. The testbed for the SAMU measurements

For each current value, an appropriate shunt was used. Figure 6 shows the testbed setup for estimating the measurement error of the voltage and current circuits. The voltage from the

voltage source was applied in parallel to all three input voltage phases of the calibrated SAMU device and to the voltage terminals of the measuring bridge. The current from the current source was applied in series to all three current phases of the calibrated SAMU and to the shunt, across which the voltage was measured by the measuring bridge.

Fig. 6. Testbed for assessing the measurement errors of SAMU voltage and current circuits

Due to the single voltage measurement input of the measuring bridge, voltage and current measurements could be performed at the same time. The measuring bridge displayed the ratio error in percentage and the phase error in minutes, calculated according to formulas 1 and 2.

V. SAMU TEST RESULTS

The current or voltage ratio error is calculated according to formula 1 and the phase error $\Delta\phi$ is defined according to formula 2 [9, 11].

$$\varepsilon = \frac{A_X - A_N}{A_N} 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\phi = \phi_X - \phi_N \quad (2)$$

where: ε - ratio error, A_X - amplitude of the current or voltage signal recreated from SV samples, A_N - amplitude of the reference analog current or voltage signal and $\Delta\phi$ - phase error, ϕ_X - phase of the signal recreated from SV, ϕ_N - phase of the reference signal. Illustration of amplitude and phase measurement errors is shown in figure 7.

Fig. 7. Illustration of amplitude and phase measurement errors

The measurement results are presented in tables II and III.

TABLE II. MEASUREMENT RESULTS OF THE RATIO ERRORS AND PHASE ERRORS FOR THREE PHASE VOLTAGES OF THE TESTED SAMU

U/U _N [%]	Phase 1		Phase 2		Phase 3	
	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]
120	-0.011	-7.6	-0.003	-8.0	0.001	-7.9
100	-0.017	-6.3	-0.003	-6.6	-0.006	-6.5
80	-0.027	-4.7	-0.013	-5.0	-0.014	-4.8

TABLE III. MEASUREMENT RESULTS OF THE RATIO ERRORS AND PHASE ERRORS FOR THREE PHASE CURRENTS OF THE TESTED SAMU

I/I _N [%]	Phase 1		Phase 2		Phase 3	
	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]	ε [%]	$\Delta\phi$ [min]
200	0.022	-4.2	0.020	-0.2	0.019	0.9
120	0.020	-4.2	0.021	0.2	0.022	1.1
100	0.021	-3.9	0.019	-0.1	0.019	1.0
20	0.056	-3.7	0.044	0.4	0.043	1.1
5	0.142	-3.4	0.158	0.6	0.092	1.3
1	0.013	-3.4	0.129	0.7	0.035	1.7

The expanded measurement uncertainty of the setup consisting of a bridge and shunts was 0.024% for the ratio error measurement and 1.9 minutes for the phase angle error. This means, that it was more than five times better than the accuracy class of the tested device, indicating the suitability of the setup for calibrating SAMU-type instruments.

The tests were carried out in the range from 1% to 200% of the rated current and from 80% to 120% of the rated voltage. The measurement results confirmed the class of the calibrated device at 0.2%.

VI. SUMMARY

The article presents the importance of digitalization of power substations in the context of the growing share of renewable energy sources and the need to ensure the stability of the power system. This allows for cost reduction, primarily related to the reduction of the amount of cabling, which has so far been the basis for the operation of measurement and protection devices. In digital substations, data is transmitted via an Ethernet connection, creating the so-called process bus. This data is delivered to the target device via a system of network switches. The requirements of the IEC 61850 and IEC 61869 standards for digital transformers and SAMU units, which process analog signals into SV data stream transmitted in real time, were discussed. The measurement results, presented together with an estimate of measurement errors and phase shifts of the tested SAMU device, confirmed its compliance with the standard requirements and its usefulness in modern digital stations. The implementation of digital measurement technology enables metrology laboratories to conduct tests of substation distribution equipment under controlled and repeatable conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hołdyński G., Skibko Z., Medium voltage switchgear equipment (Wyposażenie rozdzielnic średniego napięcia) *elektro.info* 5/2019 <https://www.elektro.info.pl/artykul/instalacje-elektroenergetyczne/129186,wyposazenie-rozdzelnic-sredniego-napięcia>

- [2] IEC 61850-9-2:2011 Communication networks and systems for power utility automation - Part 9-2: Specific communication service mapping (SCSM) - Sampled values over ISO/IEC 8802-3.
- [3] IEC 61869-9:2016. Instrument transformers - Part 9: Digital interface for instrument transformers.
- [4] IEC 61869-13:2021. Instrument transformers - Part 13: Stand-alone merging unit (SAMU).
- [5] Implementation guideline for digital interface to instrument transformers using IEC 61850-9-2, http://iec61850.ucaiug.org/implementation%20guidelines/digif_spec_9-2le_r2-1_040707-cb.pdf.
- [6] Skoczyłoda P., Sobczak M., Trzcionka S. Digital Station. Standards for Transmitting Sampled Current and Voltage Values via the Process Bus and Practical Experience from the Development of the TMU-11 Merging Unit, XXIV National Conference 2022 "Relay Protection in the Power Industry"
- [7] ZERA GmbH Operation manual WM3000U Voltage Transformer – Measuring Bridge“, Königswinter, 13 June 2017.
- [8] Fluke, July 2008 Rev. 2, 11/15A40B Precision AC Current Shunt Set Instruction Manual.
- [9] European co-operation for Accreditation (EA), EA-4/02 M:2022 – Evaluation of the Uncertainty of Measurement in Calibration, 3rd Edition, April 2022. <https://www.enac.es/documents/7020/635abf3f-262a-4b3b-952f-10336cdfae9e>.
- [10] OMICRON electronics GmbH, CMC 356 Technical Reference Manual, Version 02.10, Klaus, Austria, March 2021
- [11] Ch. Jäschke, E. Mohns, A. Mortara, E. Houtzager, B. Ayhan ENG 61 – Future Grid, May 2017 – Future Grid GOOD PRACTICE GUIDE Recommendations related to the calibration and testing of non-conventional current and voltage sensors
- [12] IEC 61869-6:2016 Instrument transformers - Part 6: Additional general requirements for low-power instrument transformers